

DIAPHRAGM FORMING OF THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES USING SILICONE RUBBER DIAPHRAGMS

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ABSTRACT

The Disciplinary group for Composite Materials and Structures has a long history of research on thermoforming of thermoplastic composites. One of these thermoforming techniques is diaphragm forming. This paper describes the development of diaphragm forming with silicone rubber diaphragms. The existing method of diaphragm forming uses two thermoplastic diaphragms in between which a laminate is placed. For laminates containing engineering thermoplastic matrices, like PEI, PPS and Peek, high processing temperatures of up to 400°C are required. A suitable diaphragm material is polyimide film. The main drawback, apart from the high costs, is that it remains plastically deformed after one production cycle. Every single product consumes two polyimide films, making the process rather expensive. The objective of this paper is to present a study on the replacement of polyimide films by reusable silicone rubber diaphragms.

Most silicone rubber suppliers produce high temperature grades of silicone that have an outstanding long term heat stability temperature of 250°C. Some claim a maximum temperature of up to 320°C. Above the maximum temperature, short-term exposure is possible, however, the time and number of cycles is not known.

A rubber sheet test set-up has been developed to investigate the behaviour of silicone rubber at diaphragm forming conditions. A single sheet of silicone rubber is deformed into a hemispherical cavity in a high-temperature environment. Displacement of the silicone rubber and deforming force is monitored. Three types of silicone rubber, certified by manufacturers for temperatures up to 280°C, have been tested in the rubber tester. With increasing temperature their stiffness decreases. At 100°C and 200°C these rubbers can be deformed twenty times in a row showing little or no plastic deformation. At 300°C the number of runs possible decreases considerably to only 7, and permanent deformation of the diaphragms increases considerably.

KEYWORDS: diaphragm forming, silicone rubber, thermoplastic composites, Mullins-effect

INTRODUCTION

Over the last 15 years extensive investigations have been carried out into diaphragm forming of fibre-reinforced thermoplastic composites (CFRTs). The most important research topic has always been the diaphragm material. In the early stages, superplastic aluminium diaphragms were used but this material resulted in long cycle times and the required processing temperature was very high [1]. Gradually, the

emphasis shifted to the polymeric diaphragm material polyimide (PI). As a result, manufacturing cycle times and thus manufacturing costs of diaphragm forming have been reduced significantly [2-5].

Although a fairly large number of CFRT aircraft parts have been produced using polyimide diaphragms, diaphragm forming of CFRTs is still far too expensive when compared with traditional metal parts on a cost-to-weight basis. A major contribution to this cost ineffectiveness is the high price of polyimide diaphragms, which also have to be disposed of after a single manufacturing cycle. Using a diaphragm numerous times would increase the cost efficiency of the process significantly.

Several investigations have been carried out into reduction of manufacturing costs through the use of silicone rubber as a reusable diaphragm material [6-8]. In all these investigations the focus was limited to diaphragm forming of mid range engineering CFRTs containing matrix materials such as PP, PA6, PA12 and PET. These CFRTs are mainly used for consumer and automotive components. However, primary aircraft structures demand the use of high-performance matrices such as PEI, PPS and PEEK, which require processing temperatures ranging from 300°C to 400°C. Research on diaphragm forming at these high temperatures using silicone rubber has not been found in the literature.

High temperature resistant silicone rubbers are available on the market that can withstand temperatures of up to 300°C. The goal of the research was to find out how long these silicone rubbers can be exposed to their specified maximum exposure temperatures, and what the influence of exposure to even higher temperatures is on the silicone rubbers. For this study three high temperature resistant silicone rubbers were selected which were subjected to deformation tests at 100°C, 200°C and 300°C. Single sheets of silicone rubber were deformed into a spherical dome-shaped female mould and required stamper forces were measured. By measuring stamper force versus rubber deflection, an indication could be given as to how increasing temperatures influence stiffness and elongation properties of the selected silicone rubbers. Furthermore, by repeating the deformation tests on a single sheet, the maximum number of test runs possible before rupture was determined. In this way the reusable nature of silicone rubber diaphragms at several temperatures was investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL

Methods

Deforming tests were conducted on an aluminium female die into which a single silicone rubber diaphragm can be deformed (see figure 1). With this diaphragm tester only single sheets can be tested, whereas during a true diaphragm forming process two diaphragms encapsulating a thermoplastic laminate are deformed. Therefore, the diaphragm tester is merely a fast and cheap tool for finding suitable types of silicone rubber diaphragms to be used for experiments in a diaphragm forming apparatus.

Fig. 1 Set-up of diaphragm tester.

Fig. 2 Diaphragm tester in oven.

The aluminium female die which was mounted on an MTS 831 elastomer test system was provided with a spherical hole measuring a diameter-to-depth ratio of 2.00 (diameter = 80 mm, depth = 40 mm). Deformation of diaphragm specimens into the female die was performed by means of an aluminium male die (stamper). Diaphragm specimens were clamped onto the mould with a clamping frame. In order to conduct tests at elevated temperatures the test set-up was placed in an oven as can be seen in figure 2.

Materials

The silicone rubbers to be used in these investigations have to meet the following requirements:

1. High temperature resistance; most high temperature resistant silicone rubbers have specified maximum temperatures ranging from 250 to 320°C.
2. Elongation properties; based on research performed on polyimide diaphragms by H.E.N. Bersee [3-5] elongation values up to 150% had to be expected. Therefore, silicone rubbers were selected that possess elongation properties of at least 150%.
3. In-house manufacturability; it had to be possible to manufacture diaphragms from silicone rubber by using a flat platen press. This factor automatically eliminated experimenting with condensation vulcanising silicone rubbers, as these require moisture from the air to vulcanise.

Three types of silicone rubber were selected for investigation; their properties are listed in table 1.

Name	Manufacturer	Max. temp. specified (°C)	ϵ (at 25°C) (%)	Shore A hardness	Specific Density (g/cm ³)	Tear strength (kN/m)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Curing type
<i>Silastic[®]M</i>	Dow Corning	250	250	59	1.29	16	4.5	2-comp. RTV
<i>Silastic[®]R^l</i>	Dow Corning	280	440	61	1.18	23	11.8	1-comp HTV
<i>P82.54.10</i>	Helvoet	N/A.	N/A.	50	1.16	N/A.	N/A.	1-comp HTV

1) *Silastic[®]R* is short for *Silastic[®]EHX60EHT00 Red3016*

Table 1 Properties of tested silicone rubbers.

Test specimens

The silicone rubber diaphragms had a thickness of 1 mm and a surface area of 160 x 160 mm. For casting the test specimens a flat plate with 1 mm thick raised borders was used. This casting mould was filled with an appropriate amount of unvulcanised silicone rubber and covered by another flat plate and then placed inside a flat platen press. For each type of silicone rubber from table 1 the following curing procedure was followed:

1. Before pressing *Silastic[®]M* specimens air was removed from the liquid-state silicone rubber using a vacuum oven. Then the casting set-up was pressed together at a pressure of 4 bar to create a 1 mm thick sheet. Finally, vulcanisation took place at a maintained pressure of 4 bar under an increased temperature of 50°C for one hour.
2. By stepwise increasing pressure in the case of *Silastic[®]R* and *Helvoet P82.54.10*, an appropriate amount of 1-component unvulcanised silicone rubber was pressed together to form a 1 mm thick sheet. Once pressure had reached 40 bar, temperature was increased to start the vulcanisation process. *Silastic[®]R* was cured at 115°C while *Helvoet P82.54.10* required a curing temperature of 180°C. Furthermore, post-curing at 200°C for four hours was performed on *Silastic[®]R*. The post-curing for *Helvoet P82.54.10* was as follows: 2 hours at 150°C, 4 hours at 175°C, 2 hours at 200°C, and finally 10 hours at 250°C.

Test procedure

Before commencing a test, the oven in which the test set-up was placed was heated to the desired temperature. Once mould and specimen had reached the appropriate testing temperature, testing of a diaphragm specimen was started by letting the stamper descend into the spherical cavity of the mould at a rate of 20 mm/min until the diaphragm was fully deformed into the mould cavity. Then the stamper force was increased to 4900 N and maintained at that value for 5 minutes in order to simulate a 5 bar consolidation phase of the diaphragm forming process. Finally, when the consolidation phase had finished, the stamper was lifted again. Such a test run was repeated 5 times without cooling the test set-up; after 5 runs the specimen was visually inspected for defects and then positioned in the mould again. A complete test series consisted of 20 runs.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The first experiments were performed on *Silastic*[®]*M* and *Silastic*[®]*R*. Tests were conducted at 100°C, 200°C and 300°C. Figure 4 shows the results of tests with a *Silastic*[®]*R* specimen at 100°C. This specimen was able to withstand a complete test series of 20 deformations without rupturing. As can be seen from figure 4, the force required for deforming the specimen decreases as the number of runs increases. However, the largest decrease in force occurs when deforming the specimen for the second time. One of the factors that might account for this force reduction is known as the Mullins-effect [8]: in uni-axial testing on silicone rubber a large permanent softening of the rubber occurs after the first cycle, with subsequent load drops decreasing when further load cycles are imposed on the rubber. As a result of the Mullins-effect silicone rubber does not fully recover to its initial size after loading; there is a permanent set after the first deformation cycle. The force reduction and permanent deformations were also found in *Silastic*[®]*M* specimens. In figure 3 an example can be seen of a *Silastic*[®]*R* specimen showing plastic deformation due to the Mullins-effect.

Fig. 3 Plastic deformation of *Silastic*[®]*R* specimen as a result of the Mullins-effect.

Fig. 4 First test series with *Silastic*[®]*R* at 100°C

During the first experiments conducted on *Silastic*[®]*R*, it was possible to complete twenty runs without specimens rupturing at 100°C and 200°C. Figure 5 shows the results at 300°C; apart from the Mullins-effect it can be seen that the diaphragm specimen ruptured during the fourth run. The same trend was seen with *Silastic*[®]*M* specimens (figure 6); again only at 100°C and 200°C the full twenty test runs were completed. At 300°C the specimen failed during the first run. Several further attempts to deform *Silastic*[®]*M* specimens at 300°C failed. As can be seen from figures 5 and 6 the specimens ruptured when the stamper was in the final few millimetres of its descent.

Fig. 5 First test series with *Silastic*[®]*R* at 300°C

Fig. 6 Results of testing *Silastic*[®]*M* in the first test series.

To verify whether failure of the diaphragms was a result of cutting of the diaphragm by the stamper at the mould cavity's equator in combination with drastically reduced mechanical properties of both *Silastic*[®]*M* and *Silastic*[®]*R* at 300°C, the equator radius was increased from 1.5 mm to 3 mm. With this modified mould a second test series was carried out with a *Silastic*[®]*R* specimen at 300°C. The result was an increase of the total number of runs possible before rupture from 3 to 5, clearly showing that an increase in equator radius has a positive effect on the life span of a diaphragm.

In a second set of experiments the influence of greased diaphragms on stamper force was investigated. Greasing of the specimens was done by applying high temperature resistant *Krytox*[®] *GPL 407* grease from *DuPont*[®] on both sides of the specimens. *Krytox*[®] *GPL 407* grease has a temperature capability of 400°C. As during the first test series, experiments were conducted at 100°C, 200°C and 300°C. Figure 7 shows the results of testing with greased diaphragm specimens. It clearly shows that with an increasing temperature the force required to deform the diaphragm specimen decreases. As expected, mechanical properties of silicone rubber decrease with increasing temperature. Figure 8 shows the effect of grease on the required force for *Silastic*[®]*R* at 300°C: appliquence of grease on silicone rubber diaphragms clearly has a positive effect on force reduction. Furthermore, the number of runs possible increased to 7.

Fig. 7 Effect of temperature on deforming force for *Silastic[®]R* (with grease).

Fig. 8 Effect of grease on required force for deforming *Silastic[®]R* diaphragm (at 300°C).

The major result of applying grease on *Silastic[®]R* specimens during the second test series being a considerable force reduction and a further increase in the total amount of test runs possible, the other two rubbers, *Silastic[®]M* and *Helvoet P82.54.10*, were also tested using the set-up. Specimens were greased on both sides and tests were conducted at 100, 200 and 300°C for *Helvoet P82.54.10*, while *Silastic[®]M* was only tested at 300°C. In contrast with the first test series at 300°C, *Silastic[®]M* did not rupture immediately during the first run. As can be seen from figure 9 it was possible to deform the diaphragm specimen for ten times in a row.

Fig. 9 Results of the third test series: *Silastic[®]M* diaphragm (at 300°C).

The *Helvoet P82.54.10* specimen (see figure 10) was able to endure 7 test runs. Greasing clearly has a positive effect on the life span of a silicone rubber diaphragm. Not only does grease reduce friction forces

between mould and diaphragm, grease also prevents the diaphragm from adhering to the mould. This adhering of the diaphragm to the mould occurred frequently when testing without grease. Figure 11 shows that increasing temperature has the same effect on the deformation force for *Helvoet P82.54.10* as it had on that of *Silastic[®]R* (figure 7): the force increases and the greatest increase occurs from 200°C to 300°C.

Fig. 10 Results of the third test series: *Helvoet P82.54.10* diaphragm (at 300°C)

Fig. 11 Effect of temperature on deforming force for *Helvoet P82.54.10* (with grease).

In figure 12 the first runs at 300°C for all three silicone rubbers are compared; as can be seen from the graph *Silastic[®]R* and *Helvoet P82.54.10* show comparable results. However, *Silastic[®]M* requires more than twice as much force to be pushed into the mould’s cavity. It seems that *Silastic[®]M* is a stiffer type of silicone rubber than *Silastic[®]R* and *Helvoet P82.54.10* when deformed at 300°C. This is in contrast with the results at 100°C during the first test series, which are given in figure 13.

Fig. 12 Comparison of the first runs of *Silastic[®]M*, *Silastic[®]R* and *Helvoet P82.54.10* at 300°C.

This graph shows that at 100°C *Silastic*[®] *R* is stiffer than *Silastic*[®] *M*. Apparently, the deterioration rate for *Silastic*[®] *R* stiffness properties is more severe with increasing temperatures than is the case for *Silastic*[®] *M*. Stiffness properties of the specimens are an important factor as stiffer diaphragms reduce wrinkling of a laminate during diaphragm forming.

Fig. 13 Comparison of *Silastic*[®] *M* and *Silastic*[®] *R* at 100°C.

In figure 14 the permanent deformation of the three rubbers is shown. The three specimens were all tested at 300°C. Further testing will have to show to what extent this plastic deformation of silicone rubber diaphragms will influence the diaphragm forming process. For example, the question whether a vacuum between the diaphragms will be able to flatten out the deformation will have to be answered. Furthermore, this permanent deformation might be of influence on stiffness properties of the diaphragm. The effect of probable stiffness decrease on part quality also has to be investigated.

Fig. 14 Permanent deformation in diaphragms after testing at 300°C.

CONCLUSION

This study has been a preliminary investigation into the possibility of using silicone rubber as a diaphragm material for processing thermoplastic composites at temperatures as high as 300°C. From the three test series conducted on *Silastic*[®] *M*, *Silastic*[®] *R*, and *Helvoet P82.54.10* the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. At 300°C silicone rubber diaphragm specimens can be deformed into a spherical shaped mould for at least 7 runs without rupturing.
2. The three specimens suffered from substantial plastic deformation after the first test run. This is very likely caused by Mullins-effect. How this plastic deformation will influence a true diaphragm forming process remains to be investigated.

3. Applying grease on the specimens lowers the force required to deform the specimens into the mould. This indicates that application of grease on a diaphragm will lower required forming pressures during a real diaphragm forming process.
4. At 100°C *Silastic*[®]*M* seems to be a less stiff silicone rubber than *Silastic*[®]*R*, while at 300°C the opposite is the case. As stiffness properties of a diaphragm influence wrinkling of a laminate, further uni-axial testing at different temperatures is required to determine stiffness differences between the three tested silicone rubbers.

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